

Case Series: Pediatric Intracranial Aneurysms in a Tertiary Level Hospital: Our ExperienceAbir Lal Nath¹, Debadatta Saha², Anindya Sundar Trivedi^{3*}¹Fellow of Neurointervention and Stroke, Assistant Professor, Dept of Neurology, Agartala Government Medical College and GB Pant Hospital, Agartala, Tripura West, India²Assistant Professor, Dept of Neurosurgery, Agartala Government Medical College and GB Pant Hospital, Agartala, Tripura West, India³Assistant Professor, Dept of Cardiology, Agartala Government Medical College and GB Pant Hospital, Agartala, Tripura West, India

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Abstract:

Intracranial aneurysms are rare in paediatric population. They have different pathophysiology, location, type, outcome than adults. Long life expectancy, more denovo formations and their tendency to recur necessitate the long term follow up in these cases. Here we summarize our experience in treating these aneurysms in a tertiary care hospital from 2014 to 2021. We found 4% of our total aneurysm population to be under 18 years with a male to female ratio of 1.5:1. 13.3% patients had multiple aneurysms and 38.9% had posterior circulation aneurysms. Most common site of aneurysm was ICA bifurcation. Most of the patients were treated endovascularly with favorable outcome at follow up.

Keywords: Pediatric Intracranial Aneurysms, Tertiary Level Hospital, pediatric population, Intracranial aneurysms.

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Introduction

Intracranial aneurysms (IA) are uncommon in pediatric population as they represent less than 5% of all intracranial aneurysms [1]. But unlike adults, they differ in their etiology, pathogenesis, aneurysm types, location, presentation and outcome [2]. Aneurysms in posterior circulation and terminal internal carotid artery (ICA) are more common in pediatric groups than in adults [1,2]. Dissecting and fusiform aneurysms are more commonly encountered than in adults [1]. Furthermore, aneurysms tend to be larger with more tendency to have spontaneous thrombosis than adults [1].

The children present with unusual headache, subarachnoid hemorrhage (SAH), cranial nerve palsy, symptoms related to raised intracranial pressure or a combination of these [3]. High index of suspicion can lead to prompt diagnosis through cranial and vascular imaging by CT or MR. Considering the longer life expectancy, IA in pediatric groups have higher recurrence rate and more de novo formations [4]. So long term follow-up schedules should be ensured.

Patients and Methods

The data was retrospectively reviewed from data base of Dept of Neurology and Dept of

Neurosurgery of Agartala Government Medical College & Govind Ballav Pant Hospital. Children of less than 18 years of age who were diagnosed and managed for intracranial aneurysms over a period of 2023 to 2024 were included in this study. Demographics, clinical information, radiological findings, treatment and outcome were analyzed. Patients who were diagnosed to have intracranial aneurysms on the basis of four vessel intra-arterial digital subtraction angiogram and underwent clipping or endovascular coiling or conservative management were included in the study.

Hunt and Hess Grade was used to grade the subarachnoid hemorrhage. A grade 0 was assigned to patients with unruptured aneurysms. A grade I to III was considered as a good grade SAH, whereas grade IV –V was considered as poor grade SAH. CT followed by DSA was done in all patients. The aneurysms were subdivided on basis of size into the following pattern –small (<10mm), large (10-25mm) and giant (>25mm). Once the aneurysm was secured by either coiling or clipping the management of SAH was consistent with the standard guidelines.

Patients were followed up after a period of 3 to 6 months after discharge from hospital. Post coiling DSA was done at 3 months. Glasgow outcome

score (GOS) was used to assess post-coiling or post-operative outcome and follow up.

Results

Patient Characteristics: In our center, 367 patients with intracranial aneurysms were treated from 2023 to 2024. Out of these patients, 16 patients were less

than 18 years. So, we found 4.4% of total population under 18 years of age. The age group ranged from 4 years to 18 years with mean of 14.8 years. Median age was 15.5 years. 1 patient was below 5 years. Boys outnumbered girls (10 boys as compared to 6 girls) with male female ratio of 1.67:1.

Table 1: Age distribution of patient

Age group (years)	Number of patients
5 or less	1
6 to 14	7
15 to 18	8

Presentation: Headache was the most common presenting feature of around 80% patients. Five patients (31.3%) had ictal loss of consciousness, 5(31.3%) had seizure and 2(12.5%) had hemiparesis. Cranial nerve involvement was seen

in 3 patients (18.8%) with the 3rd nerve being most commonly affected. Other presenting symptoms include fever, vomiting. More than 85% of patients had full Glasgow coma scale at time of presentation.

Table 2: Presenting symptoms of patients

Symptoms	Number of patients
Headache	13
Seizure	5
Loss of consciousness	5
Hemiparesis	2
Cranial nerve involvement	3
Fever	2

Hunt and Hess grading of patients are given in Table 3. Grade 1 was the most common grade seen in 6 patients. Good grade SAH seen in 13 (86%) patients.

Table 3: Hunt and Hess grading of patients

Hunt and Hess grade	Patients (%)
0	3(18.8%)
1	6(37.5%)
2	3(18.8%)
3	2(12.5%)
4	1(6.3%)
5	1(6.3%)

Radiological Findings

Computed tomogram revealed subarachnoid hemorrhage in 11 patients (68.8%). Intraventricular hemorrhage (IVH) and intracerebral hemorrhage (ICH) seen in 2 patients (12.5%) and rest of the patients had no intracranial bleed.

In our series, 16 patients had a total of 19 aneurysms. Two patients had multiple aneurysms. Eleven aneurysms (57.9%) were in anterior circulation aneurysm and 8(42.1%) were posterior circulation aneurysm. ICA was the commonest site (36.8%) of aneurysms in anterior circulation. ICA bifurcation was the commonest site of ICA aneurysms. Middle cerebral artery was involved in 3(15.8%) patients. Posterior circulation aneurysm was seen in 6 patients. Left side was involved more

commonly than right side (1.8:1). Multiple aneurysms were seen in 2(12.5%); 1 had bilateral ICA aneurysm and other had aneurysms in the posterior circulation.

According to size; aneurysms were divided into three categories: Small (<10mm), Large(10-25mm) and Giant (>25 mm). In our series, we encountered 14 (73.7%) as small, whereas large and giant aneurysms included 2 (10.5%) and 3(15.8%) patients respectively of our series. Six aneurysms (31.6%) were dissecting aneurysm, saccular aneurysm constituted 11 (57.9%) aneurysm, 1 aneurysm (5.3%) was fusiform in nature and last one (5.3%) was mycotic in nature. Predisposing factors like polycystic kidney disease and coarctation of the aorta was seen in 2 patients and all of these patients had single aneurysms.

Table 4: CT findings of patients

CT finding	Number of Patients
SAH	11
IVH	01
ICH	01
No hemorrhage	03

Table 5: Description of aneurysm

Traits	Description	Number of aneurysms
Aneurysm location	Anterior circulation	11
	Posterior circulation	08
Side of aneurysm	Right	05
	Left	10
	Bilateral	01
Site of Aneurysm	ICA –Cavernous segment	01
	ICA bifurcation	06
	MCA	03
	ACOM	01
	Superior cerebellar artery	01
	Basilar artery	03
	PICA	02
	PCA	01
	VA	01
Types of Aneurysm	Saccular	11
	Dissecting	06
	Mycotic	01
	Fusiform	01
Size of Aneurysm	Small	14
	Large	02
	Giant	03

Case 1

Fig 1- Preoperative angiogram showing Left vertebral aneurysm in v4 segment.

Fig2-Post operative angiogram showing coils in situ with stent

Fig 3- Follow up angiogram showing stent and coil in situ

15 year old boy presented to us with sudden episode of vomiting with neck pain and progressive lateral squint in right eye. We did Digital subtraction Angiogram which revealed Left Vertebral Artery dissecting aneurysm in the v4 segment.

We treated the aneurysm via braided stent assisted coiling. Patient improved over time and follow up after 3 months showed coils in situ.

Patient is doing fine.

Case 2

Fig1 –basilar artery preoperative angiogram showing saccular aneurysm

Fig 2-Balloon assisted coiling of aneurysm

Fig 3- Post coiling and follow up after 3 months showing coils in situ.

17 year old male presented to us with sudden onset headache. CT Brain suggestive of Subarachnoid haemorrhage.

We did Digital Subtraction Angiogram which suggestive of Left Basilar artery origin aneurysm. Later it was treated via Balloon assisted coiling. Patient is doing good.

Case 3

Fig1- Left ICA and Right ICA angiogram showing saccular aneurysm in ICA bifurcation

Fig 2- Ballon assisted coiling of Left and right ICA bifurcation aneurysm

Case 3 - continued

Fig 3- Post coiling angiogram of Left and Right ICA bifurcation aneurysm.

Fig 4-Follow up after 3 months.Coils in situ

17 year old female presented to us with headache and vomiting. CT Brain suggestive of Sub arachnoid haemorrhage.

Later treated via Balloon Assisted coiling.
Patient is doing fine

DSA brain suggestive of Bilateral ICA bifurcation saccular aneurysm

Case 4

Fig 1- Pre operative angiogram shows Right ICA bifurcation aneurysm

Fig 2-Post operative angiogram reveals coils and stent in situ

Fig 3- Follow up angiogram after 3 months shows coils in situ

Fig 1- Pre operative angiogram showing Right ICA bifurcation showing bilobed aneurysm

Fig 2- Post operative angiogram reveals balloon assisted coiling and coils in situ

Case 5

Fig3- Follow up angiogram after 3 months showing coils in situ

Case 6

Fig 1- Pre operative angiogram reveals Left Superior cerebellar artery Saccular aneurysm

Fig 2- Post operative angiogram reveals coils in situ.

Figure 1: Figure showing distribution of aneurysm. (ACOM: Anterior communicating artery, ICA: Internal carotid artery, MCA: Middle cerebral artery, PCA: Posterior cerebral artery, PICA: Posterior inferior cerebellar artery), VA: Vertebral Artery.

Treatment

Thirteen patients (81.5%) underwent endovascular intervention while surgical intervention was done in 1 (6.2%) patient. Two patients did not receive any modalities of treatment offered due to their financial constraints. Among total of 19 aneurysms; 8 (42.1%) aneurysms were treated with simple coiling. These aneurysms were saccular in type for 06 cases and dissecting in type for 02 cases. They were anatomically suitable for coiling without any supporting system. Glue embolization was done in 2 (10.5%) cases. Among them 01 was mycotic in nature in distal MCA and the other was small dissecting aneurysm in PICA. These aneurysms were small, thin walled; so glue embolization was preferred.

Three (16.7%) patients underwent coil embolization with supporting devices. Two (10.5%) had stent assisted coiling, one (5.3%) had balloon assisted coiling and last one (5.3%) had flow-diverter assisted coiling. Stent assisted coiling was done in case of ICA bifurcation saccular aneurysm with distal ICA-MCA M1 stenosis and giant aneurysm in left vertebral artery. Between 2 patients; 1 presented with seizure, so anti-epileptics along with anti-platelet were also advised and the other was on anti-platelets only. Balloon assisted coiling was done for small dissecting aneurysm in left vertebral artery-basilar artery junction. The giant saccular aneurysm in ICA bifurcation was treated with coiling along with flow diversion device.

Table 6: Modalities of treatment of patients

Treatment Modality	Number of Aneurysms
Simple Coiling	08(42.1%)
Glue Embolization	02 (10.5%)
Stent assisted coiling	02 (10.5%)
Balloon assisted coiling	01 (5.3%)
Flow diverter coiling	01 (5.3%)

Clipping	01 (5.3%)
Untreated	02 (10.5%)

Complications

Vasospasm was seen in 6 patients, which were confirmed by angiography and intra-arterial nimodipine was administered in patients with severe vasospasm. One patient developed arterial infarcts during the course of illness. Four patients developed hydrocephalus and among them 2 patients required CSF drainage for 3 consecutive days. One patient developed meningitis and improved with antibiotics. Other infective complications (including chest infection, urinary tract infection) were seen in 3 patients. No patient died on follow up after receiving treatment for aneurysm.

Outcome

Among 14 patients who were treated at our institute; a favorable outcome was seen in 12 (87.5%) patients. Among them, 9 (56.3%) patients were fully independent. Three patients (18.8%) showed improvement in GCS or deficit during their hospital course and were discharged in better condition. One (6.3%) patients had no improvement and 1 (6.3%) patient developed new onset deficit due to infarct at hospital stay.

Discussion

Intracranial aneurysms are uncommon in pediatric population. It represents only 0.5 to 4.6% of all IA1. We found 4.4% of our aneurysm population under pediatric group. Male children are predominantly more affected than female, with male to female ratio of 1.1:1 to 2.8:1[5]. In our series, male to female ratio was 1.67:1, which supports the male predominance of pediatric IAs. The male predominance may be due to the fact that, around one third of pediatric IAs is caused by trauma and males are more prone to it[2]. Pediatric IA differ from adult counterpart by tendency to have larger aneurysm, higher incidence in posterior circulation and ICA bifurcation, complex stricture and recurrence [2,6].

There are variations of IA among different age groups of pediatric population [6]. The anterior communicating artery (ACOM) aneurysm is rare in infants but becomes the most common site after the age of 15 years [7]. Only one of our patients had ACOM aneurysm who was 16 years of age. Dissecting IAs are commoner before 5 years of age, while classic saccular IAs occur later in life [6]. In our series, 11 (57.9%) were saccular aneurysm and 6 (31.8%) were dissecting aneurysms. Most of our patients (93.8%) age ranged from 12-18 years, which might explain the higher incidence of saccular IAs in our series. Middle cerebral artery (MCA) aneurysms and

posterior communicating artery (PCOM) aneurysms are also less commonly found than adult [6]. But, multiple aneurysms are twice as more common in pediatric group than in adults[8]. In our series we found 12.5% of our patients having multiple IAs.

Children with IAs are generally symptomatic and usually present with headache, SAH, focal neurological deficits, compressive features, seizures, ischemic features or a combination of these[2,3,6]. But non-hemorrhagic presentation is more common than adults [9]. SAH as a presenting feature of pediatric IAs ranges from 58 to 91% among different literatures [10]. In our series; 68.8% patients presented with SAH. Children presents with better clinical grades than adults with SAH2. It may be due prominent lepto-meningeal collaterals, fewer co-morbidities, increased activity of nitric oxide pathway etc [2,11].

Seizure, as a presenting feature of IAs, is commoner in children than in adults. Headache is by far the commonest symptom of pediatric IAs [2,10]. But, as these aneurysms become larger, compressive features like cranial nerve palsy, focal neurological deficits also become evident. Interestingly, cerebral infarction can also be a presenting feature of IAs, specially in case of dissecting aneurysm arising from A2 segment of anterior cerebral artery (ACA). The classic presentation of traumatic IAs is hemorrhagic episodes 2-4 weeks after a history of trauma.

Lasjaunias and colleagues categorized IAs into four types on the basis of angiographic findings and clinical scenario [11]: (1) Dissecting aneurysm without features of infection or trauma, (2) Saccular aneurysm without features of infection or trauma, (3) Infectious/Mycotic aneurysm in case of associated systemic infection or immunocompromise, (4) Traumatic aneurysm with history of significant trauma[11]. According to size, IAs can be grouped into small (less than 10mm), large (10-25mm) and giant (more than 25mm) aneurysm[3].

Dissecting IAs are usually fusiform and giant aneurysms that undergo spontaneous thrombosis[11]. They account for about 16-45% of pediatric IAs[1]. Krings and colleagues reported that the incidence of dissecting aneurysms are four times higher in children than in adults[6]. We found 21% of our patients to have dissecting IAs. Spontaneous thrombosis of IAs occurs in about 8.3 to 16.9% of all cases[1]. Angiographically dissecting aneurysms can be identified by regular or irregular fusiform dilatation usually preceded by

a stenosis that marks the proximal part of the dissection.

Saccular or 'Berry' aneurysms are rarely seen in children below 10 years of age, but can be found in up to 20% of cases below 18 years [3,11]. They are classically located at the vessel bifurcation. ACOM, MCA bifurcation, basilar top are usual site of saccular aneurysm [12].

Infectious IAs account for about 15% of pediatric aneurysms[6]. The culprit organism here is mostly *Staphylococcus aureus*, followed by *Streptococcusviridans* and other gram-negative organisms [13]. These IAs are usually located at the distal small arteries or near the skull-base. Sometimes these can be multiple, especially in immunocompromised patients [14]. On angiography they are often seen as small aneurysms arising from distal vessels extending into the hematoma [6,14].

Traumatic IAs are encountered in about 5-10% of all pediatric aneurysms [15]. 40% of these cases are found in distal ACA near falxcerebri, 35% cases in vessels of skull base and rest of the time in distal cortical vessels [6,15,16]. Usually 2-4 weeks after enduring a closed head injury, children present with intracerebral haemorrhage [6].

The site of aneurysm differs from that of adults. The most common location of pediatric IAs is terminal ICA [12]. But other common locations include ACA, MCA, ICA and basilar artery [11, 12, 17]. Posterior circulation aneurysms are three times more common in pediatric group than in adults [5,18]. The reported incidence of MCA IAs is 18% of all for both adults and children [18]. But most neonatal IAs are found in distal circulation, predominantly the MCA territory [19]. For giant IAs, incidence varies between 12% and 37% among different case series [20].

Multiple factors contribute to the development of pediatric IAs including trauma, infection, congenital vessel abnormalities, connective tissue disorder etc [19]. Hetts and colleagues grouped these factors into 'direct' primary triggers (like trauma, infection) or 'silent' genetic factors [21]. Lasjaunias and colleagues commented the pathogenesis of these IAs to be due to 'defective defense mechanism' and 'offensive etiological factors' [22]. Vessel wall dysfunction, systemic or genetic disease lead to transient or permanent failure of repairing partial insults, termed defective defense mechanism [11]. Offensive factors are trauma, infection, inflammation etc [11]. Disorders associated with these IAs include: polycystic kidney disease, fibromuscular dysplasia, tuberous sclerosis, arteriovenous malformation, vascular anomalies, cardiac myxoma, aortic coarctation, cerebraltumors, Ehlers-Danlos syndrome, Marfan syndrome, irradiation, Moyamoya syndrome,

human immunodeficiency virus, syphilis, thalassemia, glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase deficiency, sickle cell anemia, pseudoxanthoma elasticum etc [23].

For classic saccular aneurysms aging, elevated blood pressure, cigarette smoking, drug abuse, or contraceptive medication etc. are considered risk factors for adults, but these have no role in pediatric population[6]. Vasculopathy may be attributed to this pathology[2]. Dissecting aneurysms can lead to both hemorrhagic and ischemic syndromes, depending on their pathomechanics[24]. When blood enters the subintimal space through a subintimal vessel wall tear and have a transmural dissection, SAH may ensue [6,24]. Whereas, when the dissection remains subintimal and true vessel lumen remains open, then thrombi may form in the false lumen and may lodge distally in the circulation leading to ischemic syndromes [6, 24].

Infectious IAs can be seen in distal small arteries when the septic emboli lodge in the endothelium of small arteries and infectious agents spread from vessel lumen to the extra-vascular space²⁵. Larger arteries are affected when, infection extends from outside towards the lumen of the vessel or infectious emboli originating through vasa-vasorum [6]. Infectious agents can be found in blood or cerebrospinal fluid but in more than one-third cases they may not be found [6].

Treatment modality depends upon type of IAs, location, presentation, availability of skilled personnel. The modality with high obliteration and low recurrence rates with low morbidity and mortality should be preferred [10]. The reported favorable outcome for endovascular treatment was 88.3% and for surgical treatment was 82.7% with no statistically significant differences on long term clinical outcome [26]. The overall outcome was found favorable in 84.5% cases in a meta-analysis [26]. In our case, a favorable outcome was observed in 87.5% cases.

Dissecting IAs can be treated by either parent artery preserving (reconstructive) or sacrificing (deconstructive) methods [3]. Flow diverting stent is a good option for reconstructive methods which redirect blood away from dissection and press the dissecting flap against the arterial wall[3]. Coils can be used for vessel sacrifice provided collaterals are adequate [3]. In case of infectious IAs both the IAs and the source of infection should be treated³. Liquid embolics or glue can be used for ruptured IAs or for occlusion of parent vessel [3]. Traumatic IAs should also be treated by parent vessel occlusion with no attempt for endovascular filling of ruptured pouch [6]. Surgical options for treating IAs include clipping of aneurysm, ligation of parent vessel, anastomosis and bypass procedures etc [10].

The reported recurrence rate of pediatric IAs is 2.6% annually and of de novo formation or growth is 7.8% which is four times higher than adults [12, 27]. That is why, Hettis and colleague considered pediatric IAs to be potentially chronic progressive condition [21]. So, long term follow-up should be scheduled for every IAs regardless of the treatment modality used [10].

Complications may happen but the rate varies among different case series. Vasospasm, infarct, hydrocephalus, meningitis, new focal deficit, other infective complications or death are reported complications [10]. Vasospasm is probably the commonest complication with rates from 9 to 53% [10]. But it is probably more tolerated in children than in adults due to more collateral and great neuroplasticity [8, 10].

Overall pediatric population have better favorable outcome than adults[1]. But higher recurrence rate and more de novo formation are important considerations especially in case of dissecting and fusiform aneurysm [28]. A1 dissecting aneurysm rupture leads to severe hemorrhage resulting in poor prognosis and when re-ruptures has even worse prognosis [29].

Conclusion

Intracranial aneurysms are rare in children but they are getting diagnosed more nowadays. Male are predominantly more affected than female. They usually present with unusual headache, SAH, seizure or other focal neurological deficit. Besides saccular aneurysms; dissecting and mycotic aneurysms are also common in pediatric population. Though the overall outcome is comparatively better than adult counterpart; regrowth and de novo formation need to be kept in mind.

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